

Where Are You? Unscented Particle Filter for Single Range Relative Pose Estimation in Unobservable Motion Using UWB and VIO.

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Abstract—Real-time relative pose (RP) estimation is a cornerstone for effective multi-agent collaboration. When conventional global positioning infrastructure such as GPS is unavailable, the use of Ultra-Wideband (UWB) technology on each agent provides a practical means to measure inter-agent range. Due to UWB’s precise range measurements and robust communication capabilities, external hardware installations are not needed. However, when only a single UWB device per agent is used, the relative pose between the agents can be unobservable, resulting in a complex solution space with multiple possible RPs. This paper proposes a novel method based on an Unscented Particle Filter (UPF) that fuses single UWB ranges with visual-inertial odometry (VIO). The proposed decentralized method solves the multi-modal solution in 3D (4-DoF) for the RP when it is unobservable. Moreover, a pseudo-state is introduced to correct the rotational drift of the agents. Through simulations and experiments involving two robots, the proposed solution was shown to be competitive and less computationally expensive than state-of-the-art algorithms. Additionally, the proposed solution provides all possible relative poses from the first measurement. The code and link to the video are available https://github.com/y2d2/UPF_RPE.

Index Terms—Multi-Robot Systems; Localization; Sensor Fusion

I. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORKS

A. Introduction

COLLABORATING agents are required to estimate the relative pose (RP) between them. The RP between two agents is given by the six degrees of freedom (6-DoF) transformation between both agents. The RP must be estimated in real-time when considering multi-agent tasks like collision avoidance [1] or object manipulation [2]. When the global position of the agents is known in a common reference frame, e.g., by using GPS, the RP can be trivially calculated as in [1]. In the absence of a common reference frame, estimating the RP between agents is complicated by the unambiguous identification of the agents. This is challenging and computationally expensive when only relying on sensors like lidars,

Fig. 1: Four examples of unobservable RPs when combining VIO with a single UWB device per agent in 3D (4-DoF) as derived in [11]. These modes of ambiguous relative motion are unobservable, i.e., if the initial RP is unknown, the RP remains unobservable while the ambiguous mode of motion persists. For example, modes 1 and 2 can occur when moving between aisles, while modes 3 and 4 can occur during (un)loading.

radars, or cameras [3], [4]. To address these challenges, Ultra-Wideband (UWB) has gained prominence recently [5]–[12].

UWB can serve as a communication device, which allows for identification between the agents [3]. Moreover, UWB can provide distance measurements between devices up to hundreds of meters, with errors of a few decimeters when the antennas are in line-of-sight. Fixing UWB anchors on external infrastructure to directly get the RP from the pose of each agent in a common reference has been studied extensively [5]. However, this requires installation and calibration. This has led to the use of multiple UWB devices per agent to directly measure the RP [6]. However, the agent has to be large enough to enable a meaningful spatial distribution of devices. Alternatively, the RP can be estimated by sharing onboard odometry estimations in combination with one UWB device per agent [7]–[14]. When visual-inertial odometry (VIO) is used as the source of odometry, four unobservable DoF remain to be estimated since each agent can directly measure its roll and pitch angle [15]. These methods are discussed in I-B1. Generally, the initial RP is unknown. Methods that estimate this are discussed in I-B2. When only a single UWB device per agent is used, the RP can become unobservable. This is discussed in Section I-B3. Table I summarises the algorithms for RP using a single UWB device per agent and odometry.

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Reference (year)	Algorithm	Odometry source	DoF / dimension	Unknown Initial RP	Multi-modal RP	# of Agents used (sim / exp)
[8] (2021)*	NLS	VIO	4 / 3D			49/0
[9] (2021)	NLS	VIO	4 / 3D			5/2
[10] (2021)	NLS	9-DoF-IMU	6 / 3D			2/2
[11] (2023)*	QCQP	VIO	4 / 3D	✓		2/2
[12] (2019)	Algebraic	VIO	4 / 3D	✓		2/2
[13] (2010)	Algebraic	Not specified	6 / 3D	✓		2/0
[14] (2018)	MHEKF	Not specified	3 / 2D	✓ (2 DoF) ¹	✓ (2 DoF) ¹	2/2
ours	UPF with drift correction	VIO	4 / 3D	✓	✓	2/2

TABLE I: Summary of the algorithms that estimate RP using odometry and a single UWB per agent. The references marked with a star are used as benchmarks. ¹:The MHEKF assumes knowledge of the initial relative heading between the agents.

B. Related works

1) *RP estimation using a single UWB device per agent*: In [8]–[13] the RP estimation is reformulated to the estimation of the initial transformation between two agents, which changes slowly over time due to drift and exhibits lower uncertainty as trajectories extend. This gradual evolution of the initial transformation is commonly simplified by modeling it as a slow walk drift, effectively reducing the complexity of methods relying on a sliding window. However, this simplification introduces unaccounted drift between the two agents that accumulates over increasing sliding time windows [11] or with larger odometry variance. In [10], a 9-DoF IMU is used to measure the odometry, enabling the agents to express their velocities in a common reference frame. However, [10] depends on attitude measurements from the magnetometer, which deteriorates in environments with strong magnetic disturbances. When the initial RP is known, [8]–[10] rely on solving a Nonlinear Least Squares (NLS), where a sliding window is used to reduce memory and execution time. A strategy to only keep the latest measurements that increase observability is defined in [10]. In [8] a distributed algorithm is used to find the RP for multiple agents. In [7] the RP is solved by creating a pose graph from keyframes that are shared on top of the VIO and UWB. Additionally, the other agents are detected in the camera images.

2) *Unknown initial RP*: In [13] an algebraic solution is derived for the 6-DoF initial RP estimation problem. This is reduced to the 4-DoF case in [12]. However, in [11] it is shown that under realistic measurement errors, this solution is not performing adequately. In [11] the 4-DoF initial RP estimation using VIO is reformulated as a quadratically constrained quadratic program (QCQP) problem. Works [11]–[13] all require a minimum set of measurements from relative motion that leads to observable RP and do not provide a solution when the RP is unobservable. This could be a problem, e.g., when two agents move towards each other at high speed, there might not be enough measurements yet to determine the RP, which could lead to a collision. Even if there were enough measurements, this mode of relative motion would lead to unobservable RP, in which case works [11]–[13] will not provide the RP and hence not detect a possible collision.

3) *Unobservable RP with VIO and a single UWB device*: Figure 1 shows four modes of relative motion that lead to an unobservable RP. In [11] these modes are used to filter out measurements that do not lead to an observable RP. However,

it does not provide the multi-modal solution space when these modes of relative motion occur. In [14], the initial RP is solved in the 2D case using a Multi Hypothesis Extended Kalman Filter (MHEKF), in which case the multi-modal solutions are provided. However, it is assumed that the initial global heading of both agents is known in a common reference frame, which reduces the initial RP estimation to find the 2-DoF translation in 2D.

C. Contributions

The contribution of this paper is the formulation and validation of a novel decentralized algorithm to estimate the RP in 3D (4-DoF) that provides a multi-modal solution when the relative motion leads to unobservable RP. The proposed method is based on an Unscented Particle Filter (UPF), where a pseudo-state is proposed to correct for motion drift. To the best of our knowledge, no method provides RP under unobservable motion in the 3D case without a common reference frame, when VIO is shared between the agents and a single UWB device is used per agent to measure the distance between the agents. Extensive simulation and real-world experiments with ground robots have been conducted to evaluate the performance of the proposed method and benchmarked to the algorithms from [8] and [11]. The code of the proposed and benchmark algorithms, as well as the data sets, are available on https://github.com/y2d2/UPF_RPE.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the terminology is defined, and the problem is examined. Section III elaborates on the proposed approach. In Section IV, the simulations and hardware experiments are covered. A conclusion is drawn in Section V.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A. Terminology and notation

1) *Variables and distributions*: A superscript $(\cdot)^{t_k}$ denotes the value of a variable at a discrete time t_k with $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The index of the discrete time will correspond to the UWB measurements, where t_0 and t_n represent the time of the first measured distance and the latest measured distance between the two agents, respectively. Estimates are denoted with $\hat{(\cdot)}$ and measurements with $\tilde{(\cdot)}$. A Gaussian distribution is written as $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{(\cdot)}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{(\cdot)})$, with $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{(\cdot)} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the expected value and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{(\cdot)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ the variance. $\mathcal{U}(\mathbf{l}, \mathbf{u})$ denotes a uniform distribution with lowerbound $\mathbf{l} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and upperbound $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. $\text{diag}(\mathbf{X}, \dots, \mathbf{Y})$ represents a block diagonal matrix from matrices $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$.

2) *Transformations*: Following notations from [8], capital calligraphic letters denote coordinate frames. $S_i^{t_k}$ represents the body frame of agent i at the discrete time instance t_k . Due to the IMU capability to measure the gravity vector, it is assumed that all reference frames are defined with their z-axis opposite to the gravity vector. A bold capital letter denotes a matrix. $\mathbf{T}_{AB} \in \text{SE}(3)$ represents the homogeneous transformation matrix, that expresses the pose of reference frame \mathcal{B} in reference frame \mathcal{A} . \mathbf{T}_{AB} is defined by a position vector $\mathbf{p}_{AB} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{AB} \in \text{SO}(3)$. This rotation matrix is only dependable on the yaw angle, θ_{AB} , between the reference frames, due to the orientation of the z-axis of all reference frames. $\mathbf{t}_{AB} = [\mathbf{p}_{AB}, \theta_{AB}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ represent the 4-DoF states of \mathbf{T}_{AB} .

3) *VIO measurements*: The VIO measurements, $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^t} \in \text{SE}(3)$, represent the frame-to-frame transformation, $\delta\mathbf{T}_{S_i^t} \in \text{SE}(3)$, of the body frame S_i^t of agent i at continuous time t . Similar to [8] it is assumed in this paper that the states of the frame-to-frame transformation, $\delta\mathbf{t}_{S_i^t} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, of the VIO measurement are corrupted by Gaussian noise, $\mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{t}})$. $\Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{t}} = \text{diag}(\Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{p}}, \Sigma_{\delta\theta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$, with $\Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{p}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and $\Sigma_{\delta\theta} \in \mathbb{R}$ the uncertainty of the frame-to-frame translation and orientation, respectively. A piece-wise part of the trajectory of agent i between discrete times t_k and t_l can then be estimated with $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}} = \prod_{s=t_k}^{t_l} (\delta\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^s})$, where s iterates over all the frame-to-frame transformations between the time t_k and t_l . This estimate is further corrupted with high-frequency noise on the odometry pose caused by pixel discretization and is assumed to be independent and identically distributed between consecutive poses [8]. However, $\Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{t}}$ is integrated over time and causes slow changing drift on the four unobservable DoF [8]. The associated accumulated uncertainty on the states of the transformation is $\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}}} = \text{diag}(\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}}}, \Sigma_{\theta_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$, with the accumulated uncertainty on the translation given by $\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}}} = \sum_{s=t_k}^{t_l} (\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^s})^{-1} \Sigma_{\delta\mathbf{p}} (\Delta \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^s}) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, and the accumulated uncertainty on the orientation by: $\Sigma_{\theta_{S_i^{t_k} S_i^{t_l}}} = \sum_{s=t_k}^{t_l} \Sigma_{\delta\theta} \in \mathbb{R}$.

4) *UWB measurements*: The magnitude of the translation, $d_{ij}^{t_k} = \|\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_k} S_j^{t_k}}\| \in \mathbb{R}$ of the transformations between two agents i and j , $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_k} S_j^{t_k}}$, is measured by the UWB at discrete time t_k . The measurement noise is assumed to be Gaussian $\tilde{d}_{ij}^{t_k} = d_{ij}^{t_k} + \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_d)$.

5) *Unscented Particle Filter (UPF)*: In [16] the UPF is introduced, where each particle is an Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF). The reader is referred to [16] for more details. $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ represent the filter state, the input and the measurement respectively, and $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$, $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ and $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_y}$ are their respective distributions. $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ denote the prediction function and observation function.

B. Decentralised RP

This paper investigates the RP estimation between any number of agents as long as the communication bandwidth can support it [4]. It is assumed that each agent can share it is ego-motion or odometry with other agents, as well as

Fig. 2: Schematic representation of the trajectories and transformations related to the two agent RP estimation problem as explained in Section II-C. The trajectories of agents i and j are shown in dashed blue and orange, respectively. The frames are shown with a star. $S_i^{t_k}$ denotes the body frame of agent i at communication time t_k . The transformations \mathbf{T}_{AB} are shown with an arrow from frame \mathcal{A} to frame \mathcal{B} . Transformations that can be estimated using VIO are shown in the respective colors of the agents. The black transformations represent the RP between the agents, for which the magnitude of the translation can be measured using UWB.

measure the distance to these agents, similar to works [8]–[14]. The communication is assumed to occur in a peer-to-peer manner. This requires the agent's communication to be restricted to not overload the network [4]. Therefore, only the states of the odometry measurement will be communicated between two agents, at the same moment that the distance is measured between both. This has been demonstrated in [8], [11] to be feasible. It could be possible for an agent to use the inter-agent distance between two other agents as is done in [8] to improve the RP estimation of all agents. However, because the agents cannot communicate with each other simultaneously, time differences will occur between the estimated transformations. Additionally, communication should be reserved for other purposes than the estimation of the RPs, which is a tool for multi-agent collaboration [4]. This will even further increase the differences between communication times, which the solution will have to estimate. The proposed approach adopts a decentralized strategy to reduce estimation complexity and ensure real-time estimation. In this approach, each agent independently estimates the RP of agents it is in communication with. Therefore, the multi-agent RPs are replaced with multiple two-agent RPs. The method's scalability now depends on the communication bandwidth and the computational complexity of the RP estimation per agent.

C. RP between two agents

In Figure 2 the frames and transformation used for the estimation of the RP between two agents are shown. Without loss of generality, the agent doing the estimation is agent i and the agent it is in communication with is agent j . Each agent is equipped with a sensor modality, like a camera, that can estimate its odometry when combined with an IMU. Thus, each agent can measure translational and rotational velocity, as well as roll and pitch angles with the gravity vector. Each agent also possesses a single UWB device for communication and measuring the distance to the other agent. The goal is to estimate the states, $\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}$, of the transformation, $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}$, at the latest discrete time instance of communication, t_n . For this, the agents will measure the distance, $\tilde{d}_{ij}^{t_n}$, between them using the UWB (See II-A4), while simultaneously communicating their VIO estimation (See II-A3) since the previous

communication time t_{n-1} , i.e., agent i shares $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_n}}$ with agent j and agent j shares $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}$ with agent i .

Similar to [8]–[12], the RP is not directly estimated, but the trajectory of the agents since the start of communication at t_0 are combined with the initial RP to reduce uncertainty. The RP from agent i to agent j , $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}$, is then given by:

$$\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}} = (\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}} \cdot \mathbf{T}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}, \quad (1)$$

Where $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}$ is the transformations from agent i 's body frame at the start of communication with agent j at time instance t_0 to its body frame at time instance t_n . $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}$ represents the transformation from agent i 's body frame to agent j 's body frame at the start of communication, also known as the initial RP. $\mathbf{T}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}$ represents the trajectory of the agent j since the start of communication. It is important to note that estimating the trajectories of the neighboring agents in a decentralized way means that these estimates are independent of each other except through the trajectory of the estimating agent.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

To find the RP every transformation on the right of (1) has to be estimated. In this section, the solution is built up starting with only estimating the trajectory of agent j , $\mathbf{T}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}$, in Section III-A. The estimation of the initial RP, $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}$, is developed in III-B. Finally, the estimations for the trajectory of agent i , $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}$ is explained in Section III-C. Note from II-A2 the equivalency between the transformation \mathbf{T}_{AB}^t and the states \mathbf{t}_{AB}^t of the transformation, which will be predominantly used in this section.

A. Estimation of the trajectory of agent j , $\mathbf{T}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}$

First, we will consider the case where the pose of agent i , $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}} = \mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}} + \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}}, \Sigma_{\theta}))$ and the initial RP of agent j , $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}} = \mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}} + \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}})$, are measured. A trivial UKF estimates the states, $\mathbf{x}^{t_n} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, and the initial uncertainty distribution, $\mathbf{P}^{t_0} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$:

$$\mathbf{x}^{t_n} = \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^{t_0} = \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}}, \quad (3)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}$ the states of the estimated trajectory of agent j from the start of communication t_0 until the latest communication time t_n . $\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}}$ is the uncertainty on the initial RP between agent i and j . The trajectory of agent j is estimated by integrating the communicated VIO measurement of agent j , $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}$. This leads to following UKF input, $\mathbf{u}^{t_n} \in \mathbb{R}^4$, input noise, $\mathbf{Q}^t \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$, and, prediction function $\mathbf{F} \in \text{SE}(3)$:

$$\mathbf{u}^{t_n} = \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}^{t_n} = \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{t_{n-1}}, \mathbf{u}^{t_n}) = \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}} = \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_{n-1}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}, \quad (6)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}$ and $\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}}$, the states and its accumulated uncertainty of the pre-integrated VIO measurements of agent j , respectively, between the previous and current communication time, t_{n-1} and t_n , respectively. The RP, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}$, can be estimated by using the measured poses of agent i , the measured initial RP between agent i and j and the estimated trajectory of agent j by using them in (1). Finally, the UKF measurement, $\mathbf{y}^{t_n} \in \mathbb{R}$, its uncertainty $\mathbf{R}^{t_n} \in \mathbb{R}$, and the observation function $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{y}^{t_n} = \tilde{d}_{ij}^{t_n} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{R}^{t_n} = \Sigma_d + \|\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}}\| \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}) = \|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}\|, \quad (9)$$

with $\tilde{d}_{ij}^{t_n}$ and $\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}\|$ the UWB measured and estimated distance, respectively, between agent i and j . Σ_d is the UWB measurement noise. Since the pose of agent i is not estimated in this UKF, the uncertainty of this measurement is taken into account by adding the magnitude of the uncertainty on the translation of the measured pose of agent i , $\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}}$, to the UWB measurement noise.

B. Estimation of the initial RP, $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}$

In this case, the initial RP is unknown and has to be estimated. Since the uncertainty distribution of the trajectory is best represented in Cartesian coordinates, while the initial RP distribution is best represented in a spherical coordinates it is chosen to include both as separate states in this work. The states, $\mathbf{x}^{t_n} \in \mathbb{R}^8$ and their uncertainty distribution, $\mathbf{P}^{t_0} \in \mathbb{R}^{8 \times 8}$, (2) and (3), respectively, are changed to:

$$\mathbf{x}^{t_n} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}, \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}} \right]^T \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^{t_0} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{0}_{4 \times 4}, \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}}), \quad (11)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}$ the states of the initial RP transformation. As observed, the initial uncertainty on the estimated trajectory of agent j is shifted towards the uncertainty of the initial RP. The initial RP distribution forms a sphere around the body frame of agent i at the start of communication, t_0 , with a radius equal to the initial measurement $\tilde{d}_{ij}^{t_0}$. Although a UKF can work with distributions that are almost Gaussian distributions, this spherical distribution differs too much from it. Therefore, the sphere is divided into multiple particles, effectively creating a UPF. To estimate the initial RP, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}}$, spherical coordinates are employed to ensure independence from the size of the sphere, except for the first coordinate, which only depends on the UWB measurement. These spherical coordinates include azimuth $\Theta \sim U(-\pi, \pi)$, elevation $\phi \sim U(-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2})$, and heading $\theta \sim U(-\pi, \pi)$. Each angle is evenly discretized over $n_{\Theta} \in \mathbb{N}$, $n_{\phi} \in \mathbb{N}$, and $n_{\theta} \in \mathbb{N}$, resulting in a total of $n_{\Theta} \cdot n_{\phi} \cdot n_{\theta}$ particles. For each angle, the initial uncertainty is chosen such that the likelihood of being in the middle between two particles is equal to the likelihood of being on a particle. Additionally, the UPF requires a resampling strategy. For this branch kill resampling is implemented [17]. The reader is referred to the video to see this initial distribution and motion of particles in action.

Fig. 3: Intuitive representation of the effect of rotational drift around the estimating agent i . The real pose and the drifted pose of agent i and the real pose of agent j are shown in blue, light blue, and orange, respectively. At time instance t_n the rotational drift, $\theta_d^{t_n}$ of agent i is unobservable using the distance measurement $d_{ij}^{t_n}$. At the next communication time t_{n+1} after applying the VIO transformations the estimated distance $\hat{d}_{ij}^{t_{n+1}}$ will differ from the real distance $d_{ij}^{t_{n+1}}$, making $\theta_d^{t_n}$ observable at time instance t_{n+1} .

C. Estimation of the trajectory of agent i , $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}$

An important assumption of the algorithm is that the estimated trajectories are independent of one another except through the trajectory of agent i , as explained in Section II-C. Therefore the algorithm cannot estimate the trajectory, $\mathbf{T}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}$, of agent i in the individual UPFs for each agent j , since this would lead to inconsistencies over the different agents that are in communication with agent i . Therefore the integrated VIO measurement of agent i , $\tilde{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}$, will be the estimation of the current pose. This implies that the accumulated drift since the start of communication must be managed elsewhere. Furthermore, the uncertainty of the translation of agent i , $\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}}$, would increase indefinitely over time in (8), making the UKF observation step ineffective. Therefore, only the uncertainty that has accumulated between the previous communication time instance t_{n-1} and the current time t_n , $\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_n}}}$, is considered in (8). To address the drift, the VIO measurement noise of agent i from the previous communication interval, $\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_{n-2}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}}$, will be incorporated into the trajectory uncertainty of agent j . Although this works well for the translation drift, this does not cover the rotational drift as shown in Figure 3. To address this drift, a pseudo-state $\hat{\theta}_d^{t_n}$ is introduced into the UKF. This pseudo-state estimates the drift of the orientation of agent i from t_{n-1} till t_n . $\hat{\theta}_d^{t_n}$ introduces a transformation $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{\mathcal{D}^{t_n}}$, that corrects for this rotational drift. $\mathbf{T}_{\mathcal{D}^{t_n}}$ is bound to the current body frame of agent i , $S_i^{t_n}$. This implies that for each body frame that has existed up until the current time, such a transformation exists. It would be impractical to retain all of these transformations as states of the UKF. Therefore, after the observation step, when the UKF has applied the best estimated rotational drift to the current estimation of the RP, $\hat{\theta}_d^{t_n}$ is reset to zero, along with the corresponding row and column in the distribution \mathbf{P}^{t_n} . With this the state and initial uncertainty distribution, (10) and (11), respectively, become:

$$\mathbf{x}^{t_n} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}, \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}}, \hat{\theta}_d^{t_n} \right]^\tau \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^{t_0} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{0}_{4 \times 4}, \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_0}}}, 0). \quad (13)$$

The prediction function $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{t_{n-1}}, \mathbf{u}^{t_n})$ becomes:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}} = (\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_n}})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_{n-1}}} \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{\mathcal{D}^{t_{n-1}}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_n}} \\ \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_0}} = \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_0}} \\ \hat{\theta}_d^{t_n} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (14)$$

where, due to rotational drift, the first step is to backtrack the transformation from $S_j^{t_0}$ to the previous pose of agent i , $S_i^{t_{n-1}}$. This transformation is given by $(\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_0}})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_0} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}$.

Following this, the rotational drift transformation, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{\mathcal{D}^{t_{n-1}}}$, is applied. Subsequently, the previously estimated RP, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}$, calculated using (1), is employed. This rotates the previously perceived RP of agent j around the drifted pose of agent i . The newly measured VIO transformation of agent j , $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}$, can then be applied to this new RP to estimate the trajectory of agent j . Effectively, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{S_j^{t_0} S_j^{t_n}}$ does not represent the true trajectory of agent j but rather the trajectory as perceived by agent i , since all uncertainty and consequently drift on the trajectory of agent i is pushed to the estimated trajectory of agent j . Therefore, to reflect this shift in uncertainty, the input and measurement uncertainty, (5) and (8), respectively, are changed to:

$$\mathbf{Q}^{t_n} = \text{diag}(\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_j^{t_{n-1}} S_j^{t_n}}} + \Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_{n-2}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}}, \Sigma_{\theta_{S_i^{t_{n-2}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}}) \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{R}^{t_n} = \Sigma_d + \|\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_n}}}\|, \quad (16)$$

with $\Sigma_{\mathbf{t}_{S_i^{t_{n-2}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}}$ and $\Sigma_{\theta_{S_i^{t_{n-2}} S_i^{t_{n-1}}}}$ the uncertainty growth on the pose and orientation of agent i between t_{n-2} and t_n , respectively. $\|\Sigma_{\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_{n-1}} S_i^{t_n}}}\| \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the magnitude of the uncertainty on the translation of agent i between t_{n-1} and t_n .

The UKF particle is now fully developed, where the state, \mathbf{x}^{t_n} , and the initial distribution, \mathbf{P}^{t_0} , are given by (12) and (13). The input, \mathbf{u}^{t_n} , and its uncertainty, \mathbf{Q}^{t_n} , are given by (4) and (15). The prediction function, $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^{t_{n-1}}, \mathbf{u}^{t_n})$, is given by (14). The measurement, \mathbf{y}^{t_n} , and its uncertainty, \mathbf{R}^{t_n} are given by (7) and (16), and the observation function, $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}^{t_n})$, is given by (9).

IV. SIMULATIONS, EXPERIMENTS, AND DISCUSSION

We demonstrate our 3D algorithms by running the full 4-DoF estimation on 3D simulations in Section IV-B as well as 2D hardware trials in Section IV-C. For this, two state-of-the-art algorithms and three variants of our algorithm are evaluated using metrics explained in Section IV-A. The simulations of Section IV-B and experiments of Section IV-C2 compare the performance of the algorithms. In Section IV-C4 the unobservable motion experiment is shown. The results are discussed in Section IV-D. The performance benchmark, the multi-modal solution during unobservable motions, and the effects of the pseudo-state are discussed in Section IV-D1, IV-D2, and IV-D3, respectively.

Fig. 4: Boxplots of the relative position error, ε_p , and relative heading error, ε_θ of the different algorithms (see Section IV-A) from the Monte Carlo analysis of 100 simulated trajectories as explained in IV-B. The relative position error has a logarithmic scale. (Whiskers are drawn in the 1.5 Interquartile range.) The proposed solution (green) outperforms the QCQP (blue) as well as the solution without pseudo-state (red) when the initial RP is unknown. When the initial RP is known, the proposed UPF (orange) outperforms the NLS (purple).

A. Algorithms and metrics

Algorithms: The following five algorithms were used in the evaluation. In brackets behind the name is the color that represents these algorithms in Figures 4, 6 and, 7.

1) *Ours, proposed (green):* For this UPF, VanderMeer scaling points were used with values $\alpha = 1, \beta = 2, \kappa = -1$. For the initial discretization $n_\theta = 4, n_\phi = 3, n_\theta = 4$ were taken (III-B).

2) *Ours, w pseudo-state θ_d (red):* This UPF did not use the pseudo-state θ_d for rotational drift correction (III-C).

3) *QCQP [11] (blue):* The Gurobi optimization software [18] was used to solve the non-convex QCQP.

4) *Ours* (orange):* This UPF, marked with a *, is initialized with one particle with the true initial RP as value.

5) *NLS* [8] (purple):* The centralized form of the NLS was used. The calculation time was divided by two to mimic the distributed complexity. Since the NLS needs an initial RP to work with, it is marked with a *. The true initial RP was given as an initial guess. The sampling factor was set to 10.

An implementation of the Algebraic method [13] is available on the GitHub. However, due to its performance and the page limit, it is not included in this paper. All algorithms have a $10Hz$ update rate for VIO and UWB. For the QCQP and NLS a time horizon of $10s$ (100 measurements) was used.

Metrics: For the experiments and simulations, the relative position error $\varepsilon_p = \|\mathbf{p}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}\|$, the relative orientation error $\varepsilon_\theta = |\theta_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}} - \hat{\theta}_{S_i^{t_n} S_j^{t_n}}|$ and, the calculation time, t , where used. All calculations ran on Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2690 v3 @ 2.60GHz.

B. Simulations

To assess the performance of the algorithm, 100 Monte-Carlo simulated trajectories were set up, similar to [13] and [11]. The agents followed a randomly generated path with randomized start pose and velocities for $300s$. The paths were

Simulations (IV-B)	$\varepsilon_p [m]$			$\varepsilon_\theta [rad]$			$t [ms]$	
	η	μ	σ	η	μ	σ	η	μ
Ours, proposed	3.1	8.2	13	0.09	0.32	0.58		58
Ours, w pseudo-state	4.4	9.9	14	0.13	0.63	0.63		26
QCQP [11]	18	24	17	0.63	0.95	0.89		192
Ours*	<u>0.34</u>	<u>0.65</u>	<u>0.81</u>	<u>0.02</u>	<u>0.04</u>	<u>0.05</u>		<u>9.6</u>
NLS* [8]	1.2	2.7	1.2	0.05	0.13	0.17		456
Experiments (IV-C2)								
Ours, proposed	2.0	2.3	1.6	0.23	0.52	0.68		39
Ours, w pseudo-state	2.0	2.5	1.6	0.27	0.55	0.67		17
QCQP [11]	2.1	2.5	1.9	0.46	0.82	0.82		166
Ours*	<u>1.2</u>	<u>1.4</u>	<u>1.1</u>	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.23</u>	<u>0.35</u>		<u>6.2</u>
NLS* [8]	<u>1.2</u>	2.0	2.0	0.40	0.88	0.98		364

TABLE II: Results of the simulations and experiments for the error on the relative position, ε_p , the relative orientation, ε_θ and, the calculation time, t . (η = median, μ = average, σ = standard deviation, **best value for unknown initial RP, best value for known initial RP**) **Simulations:** For both the known and unknown initial RP, our algorithm performs the most accurately. **Unknown initial RP:** The proposed algorithm outperforms the QCQP (24% – 86%) on the error metrics and 69% on calculation time. The proposed algorithm with pseudo-state is outperformed (7% – 49%) on the error metrics but has 60% less calculation time than the proposed solution. **Known initial RP:** The proposed solution with known initial RP outperforms the NLS (33% – 76%), and the calculation time is almost 50 times more. **Experiments:** Similar trends are observed in the experiments, though they are less pronounced due to the maximum distance between the agents (50m vs. 8m). **Unknown initial RP:** The proposed algorithm outperforms the QCQP (5% – 60%) and the proposed algorithm without pseudo-state (–1% - 17%). **Known initial RP:** The proposed solution outperforms the NLS (30% – 74%).

Fig. 5: Two turtlebot4’s used for the experiments. The turtlebots are equipped with an OAK-D Pro camera from Luxonis. The cameras are equipped with a BMI270 IMU, that was used to measure the VIO. A Pozyx Creator tag and anchor were placed on top of the robots to measure the distance between them using UWB.

generated by a randomised acceleration $\dot{\mathbf{v}} = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1}, 0.1 \cdot \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 1}) \frac{m}{s^2} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\dot{w} = \mathcal{N}(0, 0.005) \frac{rad}{s^2} \in \mathbb{R}$ with limits: $\|\mathbf{v}\| \leq 1 \frac{m}{s}$ and $\|w\| \leq 0.05 \frac{rad}{s}$. The trajectories stayed within a sphere of radius $25m$. For each trajectory, the VIO uncertainty σ_v was changed between $0.1 \frac{m}{s}$ and $0.01 \frac{m}{s}$ with $\sigma_w = \sigma_v \frac{rad}{m}$ and the UWB uncertainty σ_d from $0.1m$ to $1m$, similar to the works [11], [13]. The results are shown in Figure 4. The top part of Table II shows the statistical results of the simulations. The bottom part shows the results of the experiments, explained in Section IV-C2

C. Experiments

1) *Experimental setup:* For the experiments, two Turtlebot4s were used with UWB devices placed on top, as shown in Figure 5. They moved only in their local x-direction, however, due to the unobservability of all 4-DoF using VIO [15], they still drifted in all 4-DoF. The agent’s ground-truth pose was tracked using a Vicon system at $100Hz$. Pozyx provided the UWB with the DW1000 chip, which provided distance

Fig. 6: Boxplots of the relative position error, ε_p , and relative heading error, ε_θ , from five experiments (IV-C2). (Whiskers are drawn in the 1.5 Interquartile range.) The light colors show the errors on the simulated trajectories (IV-C3), denoted with (sim) in the legend. The simulations and experiments show similar trends.

Fig. 7: Evolution of the average relative position error, ε_p , and relative heading error, ε_θ , over all experiments. Due to its unstable performance, the QCQP is set in a lighter blue for clarity. The proposed algorithm converges towards a more accurate solution for both the relative position and orientation than the other algorithms. The average 1σ -bound per particle (olive green) for the proposed algorithm (green) indicates that the proposed solutions is under-confident for the position estimation and over-confident for the orientation estimation, indicating potential improvement by further tuning.

measurement at $30Hz$ with Two Way Ranging. ORB-SLAM3 [19] was adapted to expose the frame-to-frame transformation as VIO at $10Hz$, using the robot’s OAK-D Pro camera with stereo inertial vision at $30Hz$.

2) *Observable RP experiment*: Five measurements of $300s$ were performed, where the agents moved by providing randomized pose targets. The maximum distance between the agents was $8m$. The uncertainty of the VIO, $\sigma_v = 0.08 \frac{m}{s}$ and $\sigma_w = 0.08 \frac{rad}{s}$ after application of a VIO outlier rejection, and UWB, $\sigma_d = 0.25m$, were measured from the experiments. The results of these experiments are shown in the boxplots in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows the average error over time. The bottom of Table II shows the statistical results of this experiment.

3) *Experimental simulation*: Due to the limitations of the experimental setup (limited distance, slow speed, and no motion in the z -direction), simulations were performed, where the ground truth from the experiments was augmented with generated Gaussian noise to evaluate the validity of the simulations in Section IV-B. The results of these simulations are shown in Figure 6 in the light colors. The simulations show the same trend as the experiments, however, in general have lower errors for almost all algorithms.

Fig. 8: Results of the unobservable RP experiment, where agent i is standing still. The trajectories of agent i and agent j are shown in blue and red, respectively, for the unobservable experiment. The dark full lines represent the real trajectories. The dashed lines represent the active particles to estimate the other agent, while the dotted light lines represent the killed particles. The big dots represent the starting point of a trajectory, and the crosses the endpoint. The black dotted lines and triangle marks represent the projection of the starting pose on the plane $z = 0$. As can be seen and explained in Section IV-C4, multiple particles remain active for the estimation of both agents. This shows the multi-modal solution in 3D for the unobservable RP when one agent is stationary. Observe the equivalency with modes three and four in Figure 1. The works [11]–[13], which do not know the initial RP, will not provide any solution for this case.

4) *Unobservable RP experiment*: As shown in Figure 1, there are modes of relative motion that lead to an unobservable RP. Two of them involve one of the agents being stationary [11]. In Figure 8, the estimated positions of all the killed and active particles, as well as the real trajectories, are shown for an experiment where agent i was stationary and agent j was driving a randomized trajectory for $60s$. The estimations of j by i are represented by four red particles for which the sum of the start azimuth uncertainties represent the full possible pose of j by i , as is shown in the video. As expected, the pose is known except for a rotation around the z -axis of i . Although not as visible, the active estimation of i by j converges towards its real pose, and four blue particles remain with the known position but uncertainties in the start orientation.

D. Discussion

1) *RP estimation performance*: The proposed algorithms are the most accurate in the simulations (IV-B) and experiments (IV-C2) in both cases when the initial relative pose is unknown (green) and known (orange). As shown in Figure 7, the proposed algorithms converged to a more accurate estimation than QCQP (blue) and NLS (purple). The QCQP algorithm does not account for VIO drift within its time window, while the NLS uses a simplified drift model. In contrast, the proposed algorithm specifically models this drift for the estimated agent (red) and both agents (green and orange). The QCQP underperformed in our simulations and experiments compared to [11]. In both scenarios, agents traveled almost

straight toward a target. Straight paths reduce the chance for significant variation in translations on the 3 axes, potentially making the RP unobservable. Since the QCQP algorithm uses measurements only within their time windows, they are less reliable than algorithms using the entire history, like the proposed UPFs and NLS. Specifically, in simulations with straight paths up to 50m, QCQP performed poorly compared to experiments with paths up to 8m. In [11], the host drone does not drift and follows a sinusoidal trajectory to ensure sufficient relative motion on all axes during drift evaluation, which could explain the difference in QCQP results between their study and ours. The length of the paths is possibly also the reason why the experiments have up to 30% lower calculation time.

2) *Unobservable motion*: In Section IV-C4, it is shown that when there is unobservable RP at the start of communication between agents, our proposed algorithm provides a multi-modal solution space that is more meaningful than having no RP estimation or a completely wrong one. Additionally, as discussed in IV-D1, RP estimation can deteriorate when the agents' motion leads to unobservable RP after the initial RP is known.

3) *Effect of the pseudo-state*: Both simulations and experiments (Table II) show a positive effect on the algorithm's performance when the pseudo-state is used (see Section III-C), confirming its importance. The effect is less strong in the experiment because the maximum distance between the agents was smaller, and thus, the effects of the pseudo-state are reduced. However, it more than doubles the computation time. Despite this increase, the computation time is still an order of magnitude less than the state-of-the-art

4) *Simulations versus experiments*: There are major differences between the simulations (IV-B) and the experiments (IV-C2) that affect the performance of all algorithms, as explained in Section IV-C3. Therefore, the ground truth data from the experiments was augmented with the estimated noise in a simulation. This showed similar trends as the experiments for all five algorithms (Figure 6), which also correspond with the simulations in Section IV-B. However, the errors in the simulation are smaller. This is mainly because neither VIO nor UWB have zero-mean Gaussian noise, as assumed in all five evaluated algorithms.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a novel approach based on a UPF to solve the most general case of the RP estimation problem using a single UWB-measured range and an exchange of VIO between the agents. The proposed algorithm tries to counter the effect of rotational drift by introducing a pseudo-state in the UKF particles, as explained in Section III-C. Simulations (3D) and experiments (2D) are described and discussed in Section IV. This discussion compares the performance of our algorithm to two state-of-the-art algorithms and shows that the proposed algorithm is better at tracking the RP when unobservability occurs during the trajectories (IV-D1), while being computationally less expensive in comparison to the other algorithms. It is shown in Sections IV-C4 and IV-D2

that the proposed algorithm can provide a multi-modal solution space when the RP is unobservable at the start of communication. Finally, it is shown that the addition of modeling the drift of the estimating agent through the pseudo-state further improves the performance (IV-D3). This makes the proposed algorithm an ideal candidate in multi-agent collaborations where unobservable motion is expected, e.g., loading and unloading, moving in parallel.

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